

Studies on weak interactions : charge transfer and hydrogen bonding interactions of chloranil with substituted benzoic acids, amines and naphthols

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Stability constants for the charge transfer and hydrogen bonding interactions of chloranil with substituted benzoic acids, amines and naphthols have been determined in hydrogen-bonded solvent CHCl₃ and aprotic solvent C₆H₆. The changes in the stability constants of the complexes in the two solvents cannot be properly interpreted but can be attributed to the variations of hydrogen bonding superimposed by charge-transfer and other weak interactions.

Hydrogen bonding plays a vital role in the stabilization of many important physiological or biological systems and exerts much influence on drug activity^{1,2}. Hydrogen bonding and charge transfer (CT) interactions may not be strong enough to form highly stable complexes but multiplicity of such bonds to receptors give them fairly high stability to form reversible drug receptor complexes. Studies on hydrogen bonding, charge-transfer and other weak interactions are thus imperative to understand drug-receptor interactions on the molecular level. Electron donor-acceptor (EDA) or charge transfer complexes are of importance as potential high efficiency optical materials³, as reaction intermediates^{4,5}, also in the field of drug-receptor binding mechanism^{2,6}. With these objects in view, we studied the possibility of molecular complex formation between chloranil and benzoic and substituted benzoic acids and reported their stability constants⁷.

The present investigation is an extension of our previous work and deals with the study of weak interactions like possibility of charge transfer and hydrogen bond formation between chloranil and various ligands such as substituted benzoic acids (not reported earlier), amines and naphthol in chloroform and benzene.

Results and Discussion

The equilibrium constant for the complex formation between D (benzoic acid, naphthols, amines) and A (chloranil or *p*-benzoquinone),

can be represented as

$$K = \frac{[AD]}{[A][D]} \frac{\gamma_{AD}}{\gamma_A \gamma_D} \approx \frac{[AD]}{[A][D]} \quad (2)$$

at low concentrations of the non-electrolytes, $\gamma_{AD}/\gamma_A \gamma_D$ can be reasonably taken to be 1.

Let C_1 and C_2 be the initial concentration of A and D and x be the equilibrium concentration of AD, we have

$$x = \frac{(d_2 - d_1)}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)l} \quad (3)$$

The equation utilized for the determination of K and ϵ_2 is^{7,8}

$$\frac{C_1}{(d_2 - d_1)l} = \frac{1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)l} + \frac{1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)(C_2 - x)l} \frac{1}{K} \quad (4)$$

(where $l = 1$ cm)

Here d_1 and d_2 represent the optical densities of A and the mixtures containing the components and complex. D (benzoic acid etc.) do not absorb in the region under study. ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are the extinction coefficients of chloranil and complex, respectively.

The constancy of the results suggests that the composition of the complexes is 1 : 1. The results are given in Table 1.

The present investigation is intended to explore the role of weak interaction in molecular complexes. Quinones, well-known acceptors, are actively associated with oxidative phosphorylation process in the electron transport mechanism in biological processes⁹ and are capable of forming CT and hydrogen bond complexes with suitable donors having marked antifungal and antitumor activities. Benzoic acid has been used as a food preservative; slightly

acidic solution prevents bacterial and fungal growth¹⁰. Benzoic acids may form charge transfer and hydrogen bonded complexes with microbes responsible for bacterial activities and fungal growth. Thus, the compounds with quinones and benzoic acids, amines etc. may have useful biological activities and the possibility should be explored.

Table 1. Equilibrium constant (K_{DA}), free energy charge of donor-acceptor complexes at 298 K

Acceptor : Chloranil						
Sl. no.	Donor	Solvent	λ_{max} nm	$\epsilon \times 10^{-2}$	$K_{DA} \times 10^{-2}$	$-\Delta G^{\circ}$ kJ mol ⁻¹
1.	2-Chlorobenzoic acid	Chloroform	374	3.69	1.62	12.60
		Benzene	336	23.04	1.26	11.98
2.	2-Bromobenzoic acid	Chloroform	374	3.25	2.11	13.26
		Benzene	336	22.95	1.66	12.67
3.	2-Iodobenzoic acid	Chloroform	374	2.71	4.76	15.28
		Benzene	336	22.65	2.57	13.75
4.	4-Fluorobenzoic acid	Chloroform	374	69.17	1.92	13.01
		Benzene	336	9.23	1.56	12.51
5.	3-Nitrobenzoic acid	Chloroform	374	2.80	1.12	11.69
		Benzene	336	23.55	3.22	14.31
6.	2-Naphthol	Chloroform	374	2.79	1.33	12.12
		Benzene	336	22.64	5.56	15.66
7.	Anthranilic acid	Chloroform	374	3.03	2.26	13.43
		Benzene	336	22.65	2.90	14.05
8.	Aniline	Chloroform	374	3.17	1.86	12.95
		Benzene	336	22.60	2.06	13.20
9.	Nitrobenzene	Chloroform	374	2.72	0.80	10.86
		Benzene	336	22.65	1.35	12.15
10.	Diphenylamine	Chloroform	374	2.90	1.00	11.41
		Benzene	336	23.55	2.37	13.55
11.	Phenylhydrazine	Chloroform	374	3.70	1.87	12.96
		Benzene	336	22.95	2.13	13.28
12.	Ethyl benzoate	Chloroform	374	2.95	1.00	11.41
		Benzene	336	22.58	2.33	13.51
13.	Methyl salicylate	Chloroform	374	3.10	2.55	13.73
		Benzene	336	23.78	1.70	12.72

It is difficult to ascertain the nature of the complexes. The complexes between quinones and benzene are regarded as dipolar complexes¹¹ or $\pi-\pi^*$ CT complexes¹². In case of complex formation between benzoquinone or chloranil and benzoic acids, naphthols etc., the possibilities are dipolar complexes or CT complexes superimposed by possible hydrogen bond formation. Complex formation is inferred from the observation of a new CT band usually in the long

wavelength region. The band is conspicuous when only the complex or one of the components and complex absorb in the spectral region of interest. But when both the components and complex absorb in the same region, it is difficult to identify the band. It is known that spectral changes are associated when a polar or non-polar solute is dissolved in polar or non-polar solvents due to dispersion interactions, dipole-induced dipole, dipole-dipole and specific short range interactions¹³ like hydrogen bonding. Spectral shifts are different depending on the polarity of the solvents and solutes. EDA or CT complex formation is usually associated with a red-shift whereas hydrogen bond formation is accompanied by a blue-shift. All these factors are superimposed when chloranil or benzoquinone interacts with benzoic acid, amines etc. and the absorption spectra of the complexes are deceptive and conspicuous CT bands are usually absent or blurred. In case of complex formation between *o*-chloranil and a series of phenols and polynuclear hydrocarbon, Roy *et al.*⁵ observed almost no shift in the absorption maximum in case of complexes but a new peak was observed when *o*-chloranil was used as the standard. It is apparent that π -electron donating capabilities of benzoic or substituted benzoic acids change with substituents and their position resulting in the changes in CT and H-bonding capabilities. The naphthols and amines can form H-bonds with chloranil. Nevertheless, the compounds have also π -electron donating capabilities. Naturally, in all cases, hydrogen bonding superimposed by charge-transfer complex formation is possible.

Comparison of the stability of the CT complexes between chloranil with benzoic acid and substituted benzoic acid gives the contribution of different substituent groups towards electron-donating capability for complex formation. The substitution effects on the donors are reflected in the association constant values.

The interaction of the components with solvents may be expected to lead to a change in the concentration for the ligand and hence a correction may be needed. The equilibrium constants of the complexes between chloranil and benzene, and chloranil and chloroform in heptane reported by Bhowmik *et al.*¹⁴ assuming no complex formation between chloranil and heptane, is also not tenable. *p*-Chloranil is known to absorb in the UV-region and absorption maximum changes with change in the solvent system. However, the effect of complex formation between chloranil (*or p*-benzoquinone) can be regarded to be eliminated as the blank solutions contain chloranil in the respective solvent systems.

The CT or H-bonding complexes have been reported to

have low K -values in the literature¹⁵. However, the association constants of the complexes have been found to be high in the present study. In most of these studies, usually one of the components was taken in large excess and the stability constants had been calculated using Benesi-Hildebrand equation¹⁶. However, from a careful examination of such constants, Foster¹⁵ concluded that most reliable data of the stability constants are obtained from optical data when the components are in stoichiometric ratio as done in the present case. This is corroborated from studies using NMR techniques. The reasons for high values of K have been explained before¹⁷. The K -values of the complexes change considerably in different solvents (CHCl_3 and C_6H_6) and the order of stability is also found to be reversed. A rational explanation in absence of gas phase data is impossible but the standard states in different solvents are different and Gibbs energy changes of the constituents may vary widely with solvents leading to differences in K -values with solvents. In general, association constants have been found to be lower in CHCl_3 compared to those in C_6H_6 though there are exceptions.

It is apparent that the contributions of weak interactions have not been properly explored and the real charge transfer spectra is obtainable only in few cases. The prototype charge transfer complex between C_6H_6 and I_2 is actually a complex held together by electrostatic, polarization and dispersion energies in its ground state¹⁸. Studies of weak interactions are, therefore, desirable.

Experimental

Chloranil (E. Merck) was crystallized from dry ether followed by sublimation *in vacuo*.

Substituted benzoic acids (2-chloro-, 2-iodo-, 3-nitro- and 4-fluorobenzoic acids) (pure, Fluka) were used as such. Diphenylamine and nitrobenzene (all A.R., Central Drug House, New Delhi), aniline (G.R., E. Merck) was twice distilled before use. Nitrobenzene (A.R.) was dried with calcium chloride and distilled (b.p. 483 K). 2-Naphthol (A.R.) was twice crystallized from alcohol + water mixtures and dried (m.p. 475 K). Anthranilic acid (A.R.) was crystallized from hot water and dried (m.p. 418 K). Chloroform and benzene were of spectroscopic grade (S.R.L., India). The solvents were distilled before use.

Chloranil and all the donors used in the experiment absorb strongly in the UV region. Chloranil when mixed with donors gave absorption curves considerably different from that of chloranil. Though there was little or no shift in the absorption maxima but the absorptivity values were considerably increased, indicating possible complex formation.

However, since all the components absorb strongly in the UV region, superimposition of absorption curves make the identification of the complexes difficult in the UV region. However, chloranil also shows weak and broad absorption band in the longer wavelength region (300–420 nm) having maxima near 373 and 336 nm in CHCl_3 and C_6H_6 , respectively, where other components do not absorb. Thus, these wavelengths were favoured for the study. Chloranil when mixed with the donor showed no shift or slight shift in the absorption maximum but the absorptivity values considerably increased similar to the observations made by other workers^{6,19}. Thus, the absorption maximum of chloranil (373.3 nm) shifted to 371.7 nm with the addition of benzoic acids. Observations were similar in other cases also. However, for the determination of association constant, 370 (CHCl_3) and 336 nm (CCl_4) were selected in all cases for convenience where the differences in the absorptivity values of the mixtures and chloranil were found to be maximum in most cases.

For the determination of the association constants of the complexes, chloranil and the donors were usually mixed in the stoichiometric ratios. In order to get accurate results, the absorptivity values of the mixtures and chloranil were kept within 0.200–0.630.

Shimadzu UV2201 and Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometers controlled at 298 K, were used.

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